

1 **DMRT1 epigenetic control through Dlx5.**

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6 We identified *DMRT1* interaction partners by ectopic expression of DMRT1 in a human primordial
7 germ-like stem cell culture system coupled with measurement of total transcription by next generation
8 RNA-sequencing. DMRT1 interacted with the imprinting axis involving Xist-Dlx-Olig activation-repression
9 through Dlx5. A second key transcriptional partner of DMRT1 in epigenetic reprogramming was Zic5.

10 Citations

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